

Appendix B - Proving Zero-Knowledge Using PEPL+IS

Andrew David Hulme¹, Boris Konev¹, and Alexei Lisitsa¹

University of Liverpool, Liverpool, UK
{A.D.Hulme,Konev,Lisitsa}@liverpool.ac.uk

1 3-Colourability

Example. 3-Colourability is a classic problem that has a nice and intuitive zero-knowledge proof. The problem begins with a graph: A set of vertices that have edges connecting them. It is always possible to colour these vertices such that no two vertices connected by an edge are the same colour. However, is this possible with only three colours? 3-Colourability is a property of a graph saying it is indeed possible. The witness to this statement is then a colouring for each vertex that follows these restrictions.

A proof system for this statement is a protocol that convinces the Verifier that the Prover has this colouring, which could be done simply by giving them the colouring and having the Verifier check that the colouring is valid. For this proof system to be zero-knowledge, we can use the following protocol specification:

1. The Prover takes their colouring (witness) and permutes those colours by one of the six possible derangements of three elements.
2. The Prover encrypts each of the deranged colourings independently and sends the whole encrypted colouring to the Verifier.
3. The Verifier requests to see the colouring of two vertices connected by an edge.
4. The Prover sends the key to decrypt the colouring of those two vertices.
5. The Verifier decrypts these vertices' colourings and checks that they are not the same.
6. Repeat with random permutations and edges until the Verifier is satisfied.

This specification shows a step-by-step proof system that can be proven to be zero-knowledge. However, for PEPL+IS to be properly used, it is poorly defined. Each step can be split into multiple smaller steps, showing that they are a composition of multiple actions. Some areas are poorly communicated, like how the link between colours and vertices works, or how the encryption maintains this connection. The conversion of this specification into PEPL+IS will clarify these areas.

Separating these into singular actions we get:

1. **choDer**: The Prover randomly selects a permutation.
2. **appDer**: The Prover applies this permutation to their colouring of vertices.
3. **choKey**: The Prover randomly generates an encryption/decryption pair of keys for each vertex.
4. **encCol**: The Prover encrypts each vertex's colouring with its encryption key.
5. **sendCom**: The Prover sends this encrypted colouring to the Verifier.
6. **recCom**: The Verifier receives the encrypted colouring.
7. **choEdge**: The Verifier randomly selects an edge of the graph.
8. **sendEdge**: The Verifier sends a request of this edge to the Prover.
9. **recEdge**: The Prover receives the edge request.
10. **getKey**: The Prover finds the decryption keys for the vertices connected by this edge.
11. **sendKey**: The Prover sends these decryption keys to the Verifier.
12. **recKey**: The Verifier receives these decryption keys.
13. **decCol**: The Verifier decrypts the colourings of the vertices connected by the requested edge.
14. **passCol**: The colourings of the two vertices are different.
15. **failCol**: The colourings of the two vertices are the same, or use an unrecognised colour.
16. Repeat.

Actions that have multiple possible results are then split. **choDer** is a choice between 6 different derangements, so it splits into 6 actions. Thus, we get $\text{choDer}_1, \dots, \text{choDer}_6$ with propositions d_1, \dots, d_6 for each resulting derangement. This gives a precondition of $\text{pre}(\text{choDer}_1) = d_1 \wedge \neg(d_2 \vee \dots \vee d_6)$ and similarly for the others.

This then impacts the next action's precondition, $\text{pre}(\text{appDer})$, includes $\bigvee_{i=1}^6 K_P(\text{pre}(\text{choDer}_i))$.

A choice that does not impact the information the Verifier can gain about the witness is **choKey**. As such, we can abstract from the many possible keys that could be chosen, and the action remains singular. Therefore, there is no need to assign any propositions, or change the precondition.

The choice of a random edge from the graph comes from **choEdge**. Therefore, the number of outcomes is based on the size of the graph, so we need a representation of the number of edges of the graph. We can denote this with n , which will be held in an agent's information set. Thus, we get $\text{choEdge}_1, \dots, \text{choEdge}_n$, and propositions e_1, \dots, e_n . This gives similar preconditions to choosing the derangement, with $\text{pre}(\text{choEdge}_1) = e_1 \wedge \neg(e_2 \vee \dots \vee e_n)$. Following this similarity, the next action's precondition is affected, with $\text{pre}(\text{sendEdge})$ including $\bigvee_{i=1}^n K_V(\text{pre}(\text{choEdge}_i))$.

In terms of indistinguishability, the actions undertaken by a party are distinguishable by that party, and the communication channel can only distinguish

the actions that involve communication through it. Recall that ι is the identity action with $\text{pre}(\iota) = \top$, and that indistinguishability is a transitive relation.

- $\text{choDer}_i \sim_V \text{appDer} \sim_V \text{choKey} \sim_V \text{encCol} \sim_V \text{sendCom} \sim_V \iota$.
- $\text{sendCom} \not\sim_c \iota \not\sim_c \text{recCom}$.
- $\text{recCom} \sim_P \text{choEdge}_i \sim_P \text{sendEdge} \sim_P \iota$.
- $\text{sendEdge} \not\sim_c \iota \not\sim_c \text{recEdge}$.
- $\text{recEdge} \sim_V \text{getKey} \sim_V \text{sendKey} \sim_V \iota$.
- $\text{sendKey} \not\sim_c \iota \not\sim_c \text{recKey}$.
- $\text{recKey} \sim_P \text{decCol} \sim_P \text{passCol} \sim_P \text{failCol} \sim_P \iota$.

Unless stated here, all other actions are distinguishable by agents P the Prover and V the Verifier, whereas all other actions are indistinguishable from ι for c the communication channel.

For dependencies, we need to directly consider when an action is allowed to occur. This needs basic justifications, like how you cannot apply a derangement to the witness until you have selected one. However, you can show more subtle orderings, like being able to choose the encryption/decryption keys at any point before the encryption.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{dep}(\text{choDer}_i) &= \text{dep}(\text{choKey}) = \text{dep}(\text{choEdge}) = \top, \\
 \text{dep}(\text{appDer}) &= \bigvee_{i=1}^6 \text{choDer}_i, & \text{dep}(\text{encCol}) &= \text{choKey}, \\
 \text{dep}(\text{sendCom}) &= \text{encCol}, & \text{dep}(\text{recCom}) &= \text{sendCom}, \\
 \text{dep}(\text{sendEdge}) &= \bigvee_{i=1}^n \text{choEdge}_i, & \text{dep}(\text{recEdge}) &= \text{sendEdge}, \\
 \text{dep}(\text{getKey}) &= \text{recEdge}, & \text{dep}(\text{sendKey}) &= \text{getKey}, \\
 \text{dep}(\text{recKey}) &= \text{sendKey}, & \text{dep}(\text{decCol}) &= \text{recKey}, \\
 \text{dep}(\text{passCol}) &= \text{dep}(\text{failCol}) = \text{decCol}, \\
 \text{dep}(\text{fin}) &= \text{passCol} \vee \text{failCol}.
 \end{aligned}$$

We also need a representation for the witness, both as a first-order sentence and as a proposition. In the epistemic model, we represent the witness with w and add it as a prerequisite for appDer , as that is the point in which a colouring is needed. Thus, we have $\text{pre}(\text{appDer}) = K_P w \wedge (\bigvee_{i=1}^6 K_P(\text{pre}(\text{choDer}_i)))$. For the witness' first-order theorem, we need to go over what information each agent holds.

In the initial epistemic model, the information held by each agent at the beginning of the proof system is contained in their information sets. For the communication channel, this is nothing, so $I_c(s) = Ax_c(s) = \emptyset$ for all states $s \in S$ in the model. For the Verifier, they start with information held by both parties. This would be the graph, which is represented as a set of vertices and

edges. We have $\text{Vert} = \{v_1, \dots, v_m\}$, $\text{Edge} = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$, which means both m and n are also held in the information sets. The elements of Edge use the same symbol as the edge propositions to show their link and are differentiated based on context. These sets are related with an axiom

$$\forall e \in \text{Edge}(\exists v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(e, v_1, v_2)))$$

and to make things easier later, we can simplify the predicate

$$\forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(v_1, v_2) \leftrightarrow \exists e \in \text{Edge}(\text{Con}(e, v_1, v_2))).$$

Note that to prevent edges connecting more than two vertices, we need to add

$$\begin{aligned} \forall e \in \text{Edge}, \forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(e, v_1, v_2) \rightarrow \\ \forall v_3, v_4 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(e, v_3, v_4) \rightarrow v_3 = v_1 \wedge v_4 = v_2 \vee v_3 = v_2 \wedge v_4 = v_1)). \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we don't want any single-vertex loops, so

$$\forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(v_1, v_2) \rightarrow v_1 \neq v_2).$$

With this, we can define a witness as a function Col assigning each vertex a colour:

$$\forall v \in \text{Vert}(\text{Col}(v) = r \vee \text{Col}(v) = g \vee \text{Col}(v) = b),$$

with the added restriction

$$\forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(v_1, v_2) \rightarrow \text{Col}(v_1) \neq \text{Col}(v_2)).$$

We also need to quantify the maximal amount of information a Prover without the witness can know. In that case, we get

$$\exists v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(v_1, v_2) \wedge \text{Col}(v_1) = \text{Col}(v_2)) \vee$$

$$\exists v \in \text{Vert}(\text{Col}(v) \neq r \wedge \text{Col}(v) \neq g \wedge \text{Col}(v) \neq b).$$

For the full definition, we use w to represent the state in which the witness is true, and \bar{w} for the state where it isn't. If an agent cannot distinguish an action from the identity, we don't include their information set since it would be empty. As communication is sending information held by an agent, the agent sending the information gains nothing and so their information set is also empty.

We can now give the full definition of the information sets and axioms for all states in the initial epistemic model and actions of the action model:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_V(w) &= \{m, n, \text{Vert} = \{v_1, \dots, v_m\}, \text{Edge} = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}, \text{RGB} = \{0, 1, 2\} \\
 &\quad \text{RGBX} = (\text{RGB} \cup \{*\})\} \\
 Ax_V(w) &= \{\forall e \in \text{Edge}, \exists v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(e, v_1, v_2)), \\
 &\quad \forall e \in \text{Edge}, v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4 \in \text{Vert}((\text{Con}(e, v_1, v_2) \wedge \text{Con}(e, v_3, v_4)) \rightarrow \\
 &\quad \quad ((v_1 = v_3 \wedge v_2 = v_4) \vee (v_1 = v_4 \wedge v_2 = v_3))), \\
 &\quad \forall e_1, e_2 \in \text{Edge}, v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}((\text{Con}(e_1, v_1, v_2) \wedge \text{Con}(e_2, v_1, v_2)) \rightarrow \\
 &\quad \quad e_1 = e_2), \\
 &\quad \forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(v_1, v_2) \leftrightarrow \exists e \in \text{Edge}(\text{Con}(e, v_1, v_2))), \\
 &\quad \forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(v_1, v_2) \rightarrow v_1 \neq v_2), \\
 &\quad \forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(v_1, v_2) \rightarrow \text{Con}(v_2, v_1))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_P(w) &= I_V(w) \cup \{\text{Col} : \text{Vert} \rightarrow \text{RGBX}, K = \{k_1, \dots\}\} \\
 Ax_P(w) &= Ax_V(w) \cup \{\forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(v_1, v_2) \rightarrow \text{Col}(v_1) \neq \text{Col}(v_2)), \\
 &\quad \forall v \in \text{Vert}(\text{Col}(v) \in \text{RGB})\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_V(\bar{w}) &= I_V(w), & Ax_V(\bar{w}) &= Ax_V(w) \\
 I_P(\bar{w}) &= I_V(\bar{w}) \cup \{\text{Col} : \text{Vert} \rightarrow \text{RGBX}, K = \{k_1, \dots\}\} \\
 Ax_P(\bar{w}) &= Ax_V(\bar{w}) \cup \{(\exists v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}((\text{Col}(v_1) = *) \vee \\
 &\quad (\text{Con}(v_1, v_2) \wedge \text{Col}(v_1) = \text{Col}(v_2))))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_P(\text{choDer}_i) &= \{d : RGB \rightarrow RGB\} \\
Ax_P(\text{choDer}_i) &= \{\forall c_1, c_2 \in RGB (c_1 \neq c_2 \leftrightarrow d(c_1) \neq d(c_2))\} \\
I_P(\text{appDer}) &= \{\text{Der} : \text{Vert} \rightarrow RGB\} \\
Ax_P(\text{appDer}) &= \{\forall v \in \text{Vert} (\text{Der}(v) = d(\text{Col}(v)))\} \\
I_P(\text{choKey}) &= \{K_m = \{k_1, \dots, k_m\}\} \\
Ax_P(\text{choKey}) &= \{\forall k \in K_m (k \in K), \forall v \in \text{Vert} (\exists k \in K_m (\text{key}(v, k))), \\
&\quad \forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}, \forall k_1, k_2 \in K_m ((\text{key}(v_1, k_1) \wedge \text{key}(v_2, k_2)) \rightarrow \\
&\quad (v_1 = v_2 \leftrightarrow k_1 = k_2))\} \\
I_P(\text{encCol}) &= \{\text{Com} = \{c_1, \dots, c_m\}\} \\
Ax_P(\text{encCol}) &= \{\forall v \in \text{Vert}, k \in K_m (\text{key}(v, k) \rightarrow \\
&\quad \exists c \in \text{Com} (c = \text{Enc}(\text{Der}(v), k)) \wedge \text{Der}(v) = \text{Dec}(c, k)), \\
&\quad \forall v \in \text{Vert}, k \in K_m, c \in \text{Com} (\\
&\quad (\text{key}(v, k) \wedge c = \text{Enc}(\text{Der}(v), k)) \leftrightarrow \text{link}(v, c)), \\
&\quad \forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}, \forall k_1, k_2 \in K_m (\text{Enc}(v_1, k_1) = \text{Enc}(v_2, k_2) \leftrightarrow \\
&\quad (v_1 = v_2 \wedge k_1 = k_2)), \\
&\quad \forall c \in \text{Com}, \forall k, k' \in K_m ((\text{Dec}(c, k) \in RGB \wedge k \neq k') \rightarrow \\
&\quad \text{Dec}(c, k') \notin RGB)\} \\
I_c(\text{sendCom}) &= \{m, \text{Vert} = \{v_1, \dots, v_m\}, \text{Com} = \{c_1, \dots, c_m\}\} \\
Ax_c(\text{sendCom}) &= \{\forall v \in \text{Vert}, \exists c \in \text{Com} (\text{link}(v, c)), \\
&\quad \forall c \in \text{Com}, \exists v \in \text{Vert} (\text{link}(v, c)), \\
&\quad \forall c_1, c_2 \in \text{Com}, \forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert} (\\
&\quad (\text{link}(v_1, c_1) \wedge \text{link}(v_2, c_2)) \rightarrow (v_1 = v_2 \leftrightarrow c_1 = c_2))\} \\
I_V(\text{recCom}) &= \{m, \text{Vert} = \{v_1, \dots, v_m\}, \text{Com} = \{c_1, \dots, c_m\}\} \\
Ax_V(\text{sendCom}) &= \{\forall v \in \text{Vert}, \exists c \in \text{Com} (\text{link}(v, c)), \\
&\quad \forall c \in \text{Com}, \exists v \in \text{Vert} (\text{link}(v, c)), \\
&\quad \forall c_1, c_2 \in \text{Com}, \forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert} (\\
&\quad (\text{link}(v_1, c_1) \wedge \text{link}(v_2, c_2)) \rightarrow (v_1 = v_2 \leftrightarrow c_1 = c_2))\} \\
I_V(\text{choEdge}_i) &= \{e\}, \quad Ax_V(\text{choEdge}_i) = \{e \in \text{Edge}\} \\
I_c(\text{sendEdge}) &= \{e\}, \quad Ax_c(\text{sendEdge}) = \{e \in \text{Edge}\} \\
I_P(\text{recEdge}) &= \{e\}, \quad Ax_P(\text{recEdge}) = \{e \in \text{Edge}\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_P(\text{getKey}) &= \{k_1, k_2\} \\
 Ax_P(\text{getKey}) &= \{\exists v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(Con(e, v_1, v_2) \wedge key(v_1, k_1) \wedge \\
 &\quad key(v_2, k_2)), \\
 &\quad \exists c_1, c_2 \in \text{Com}(Dec(c_1, k_1) \in \text{RGB} \wedge \\
 &\quad Dec(c_2, k_2) \in \text{RGBX})\} \\
 I_c(\text{sendKey}) &= \{k_1, k_2\} \\
 Ax_c(\text{sendKey}) &= \{\exists v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(Con(e, v_1, v_2) \wedge key(v_1, k_1) \wedge \\
 &\quad key(v_2, k_2)), \\
 &\quad \exists c_1, c_2 \in \text{Com}(Dec(c_1, k_1) \in \text{RGB} \wedge \\
 &\quad Dec(c_2, k_2) \in \text{RGBX})\} \\
 I_V(\text{recKey}) &= \{k_1, k_2\} \\
 Ax_V(\text{recKey}) &= \{\exists v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(Con(e, v_1, v_2) \wedge key(v_1, k_1) \wedge \\
 &\quad key(v_2, k_2)), \\
 &\quad \exists c_1, c_2 \in \text{Com}(Dec(c_1, k_1) \in \text{RGB} \wedge \\
 &\quad Dec(c_2, k_2) \in \text{RGBX})\} \\
 I_V(\text{decCol}) &= \{r_1, r_2\} \\
 Ax_V(\text{decCol}) &= \{\exists c_1, c_2 \in \text{Com}(key(c_1, k_1) \wedge key(c_2, k_2) \wedge \\
 &\quad r_1 = Dec(c_1, k_1) \wedge r_2 = Dec(c_2, k_2))\} \\
 I_V(\text{passCol}) &= \emptyset \\
 Ax_V(\text{passCol}) &= \{r_1 \neq r_2 \wedge r_1 \in \text{RGB} \wedge r_2 \in \text{RGB}\} \\
 I_V(\text{failCol}) &= \emptyset \\
 Ax_V(\text{failCol}) &= \{r_1 = r_2 \vee \neg(r_1 \in \text{RGB} \wedge r_2 \in \text{RGB})\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Using these axioms, we can derive the maximal probabilities for the probabilistic actions, including the chance of failure. Failure is described in `failCom` as the property $r_1 = r_2 \vee \neg(r_1 \in \text{RGB} \wedge r_2 \in \text{RGB})$. From earlier axioms, we can conclude that $r_1, r_2 \in \text{RGBX}$, and that they are both a decryption of a committed colouring. Thus, they originate from the Prover's original colouring in which we have $\forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(Con(v_1, v_2) \rightarrow Col(v_1) \neq Col(v_2))$. As we can also show that the colourings r_1 and r_2 are of vertices connected by an edge, this must also be true for these. Hence, this failure condition contradicts the information held by the Prover in that world. The other failure condition, that the one of the colouring's is invalid, is also contradicted. Notably, this proves the protocol's completeness as it is impossible for a Prover with a witness to meet a failure condition without a contradiction in the first order structure. These axioms are necessary by the chain of dependence that comes from *fin* requiring the actions that add them.

In the other world, where the Prover does not have a witness, we have a definition that does not contradict the failure condition. Indeed, it ensures that such a condition must exist. However, this property also does not contradict the passing theorem in `passCol`. As such, it is possible to succeed even if it is not guaranteed. Now we want to deduce the maximal chance that this pass occurs, but first we must prove the protocol's soundness.

For computational soundness we need to prove that it is impossible for a Prover without the witness to always succeed. This is done through the previous showing that failure is always possible. However, there are more caveats to address. These must be done through the collective first-order structure that represents the different states of the epistemic model as situations in situation calculus.

Through the axioms of `failCol`, we have a necessary condition for failure in r_1 and r_2 . These can be traced through their definition to the keys k_1 and k_2 , which in turn originate from the edge e chosen by the Verifier. This is the point in the epistemic model that splits states into different possibilities based on the chosen edge. Here, we can model a congregation of structures.

Under the original epistemic state \bar{w} , a slice of the epistemic model following the update of `choEdgei`, given that the dependencies are fulfilled, will be n -many states, each of which having a single e_i proposition true and the others false. In each of these states, the Verifier learns of the constant e and the axiom $e \in \text{Edge}$. Convert each of these states into situation calculus and we can show that

$$\forall s \in \text{Situ}, \exists e \in \text{Edge}(e^s(s, e)),$$

where the predicate e is the converted constant from each situation.

We can now add further meta-information about the difference between each state. As each situation represents a state with a different proposition e_i representing a different edge, we therefore say that

$$\forall e_1, e_2 \in \text{Edge}, \forall s_1, s_2 \in \text{Situ}(e^s(s_1, e_1) \wedge e^s(s_2, e_2) \rightarrow (s_1 \neq s_2 \leftrightarrow e_1 \neq e_2)).$$

Each situation represents a state and the slice of the epistemic model had n -many states for each proposition representing an edge. Thus, we can conclude, by the pigeon-hole principle,

$$\forall e \in \text{Edge}, \exists s \in \text{Situ}(e^s(s, e)).$$

Thus, any failing edge that must exist in \bar{w} must be reachable by the proof system.

To properly prove soundness, the reachability of this edge must not be controlled by the Prover as this could remove the chance of reaching it. Instead, it is either randomly decided or chosen by the Verifier. In this case, the choice is made by the Verifier so the failing edge could always possibly be chosen.

We can equivalently prove computational soundness with a different construction. If we create a congregated structure after `passCol`, with fulfilled dependencies, we find that

$$\forall s \in \text{Situ}(\exists e \in \text{Edge}, v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}^s(s, e, v_1, v_2) \wedge \text{Col}(v_1) \neq \text{Col}(v_2) \wedge \text{Col}(v_1) \in \text{RGB} \wedge \text{Col}(v_2) \in \text{RGB})).$$

Through similar rhetoric to before, this is true for every state, and every state has a different edge. There are as many states as there are edges, thus

$$\forall e \in \text{Edge}, \exists s \in \text{Situ}, v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}^s(s, e, v_1, v_2) \wedge \text{Col}(v_1) \neq \text{Col}(v_2) \wedge \text{Col}(v_1) \in \text{RGB} \wedge \text{Col}(v_2) \in \text{RGB})).$$

Through this we can now conclude that if these are all true through the single commitment `Com`, the colouring that created this commitment must have that

$$\forall e \in \text{Edge}, \exists v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(e, v_1, v_2) \wedge \text{Col}(v_1) \neq \text{Col}(v_2) \wedge \text{Col}(v_1) \in \text{RGB} \wedge \text{Col}(v_2) \in \text{RGB})),$$

which is a constraint that the definition of a witness fulfils. Thus, a Prover who can always succeed must necessarily have some information which holds a property held by the witness. As there is a direct one-to-one equivalence of this restriction to the witness' definition, we can say that having a witness means the Prover will always succeed, which means the protocol is complete.

As the failure condition has been shown to be linked to a failing edge, it is simple to see that the minimal number of failing edges is 1. As there are n -many edges, assuming the uniform probability of choice, the chance of failure is then at least $\frac{1}{n}$. Similarly, the chance of success is at most $\frac{n-1}{n}$. Thus, we get $\mathbb{L}(\bar{w})(\text{failCol}) = \frac{1}{n}$ and $\mathbb{L}(\bar{w})(\text{passCol}) = \frac{n-1}{n}$. Here, \bar{w} is the probabilistic state with precondition $\text{pre}(\bar{w}) = \neg w$. Since all edges are valid if a true witness is present, we have probabilities 1 and 0 for the probabilistic state w , where $\text{pre}(w) = w$. These preconditions fulfil the properties that $w \wedge \neg w \iff \perp$ and $w \vee \neg w \iff \top$, thus they are valid preconditions for the probability states.

Computational soundness can now be shown based on a negligible probability of success. Given a negligible probability $0 < \epsilon < 1$, we want to show that the proof system can guarantee a probability of cheating of at most this. We know that the probability of a Prover, without a witness, succeeding is at most $\frac{n-1}{n}$. This remains true between each iteration of the proof system as each instance is assumed to be completely independent. Thus, we want some number of iterations l such that $(\frac{n-1}{n})^l < \epsilon$. $0 < \frac{n-1}{n} < 1$ so $l \times \ln(\frac{n-1}{n}) < \ln(\frac{n-1}{n}) < 0$, thus we can rearrange to $l > \left(\frac{\ln \epsilon}{\ln \frac{n-1}{n}}\right)$. As both the numerator and denominator are less than 0, the number of iterations is positive and finite. Thus, the proof system is computationally sound.

To prove zero-knowledge, we now need to define a probabilistic polynomial-time simulator that mimics the proof system from the Verifier’s point of view. Since the simulator has no witness, a malicious attempt must be generated instead. To properly simulate the proof system, this simulator must cover all possible information that the Verifier can learn about the witness through the protocol. In this case, that would be the existence of a valid edge, as shown by the axioms of `passCol`. Thus, the simulator first generates a single random, valid edge which it uses to attempt to convince the Verifier.

1. The Simulator selects a random edge and gives its vertices a random valid colouring.
2. The rest of the vertices are left blank, and the Simulator encrypts this colouring.
3. This encrypted colouring is ‘sent’ to the Verifier, who responds with the request of an edge.
4. The Simulator sends the keys for the colouring of the vertices connected by this edge.
5. The Verifier decrypts these colourings and checks their validity.

Since this protocol is simulated entirely by the Verifier, the concept of ‘sending’ is incorrect. However, it will be used to properly show the necessary separation between the simulator and the Verifier within the simulation. Since it must be proven separately, actions done by the Verifier that should be equivalent in both protocols will be initially named differently, with an additional ‘.

1. `ranEdgei`: The Simulator chooses a random edge from the graph.
2. `genColj`: The Simulator chooses a random valid colouring for the vertices connected by that edge, all other vertices are uncoloured.
3. `choKey’`: The Simulator randomly generates an encryption/decryption pair of keys for each vertex.
4. `encCol’`: The Simulator encrypts each vertex’s colouring (or lack of) with its encryption key.
5. `sendCom’`: The Simulator sends this encrypted colouring to the Verifier.
6. `recCom’`: The Verifier receives the encrypted colouring.
7. `choEdge’i`: The Verifier random selects an edge of the graph.
8. `sendEdge’`: The Verifier sends a request of this edge to the Simulator.
9. `recEdge’`: The Simulator receives the edge request.
10. `getKey’`: The Simulator find the decryption keys for the vertices connected by this edge.
11. `sendKey’`: The Simulator sends these decryption keys to the Verifier.
12. `recKey’`: The Verifier receives these decryption keys.
13. `decCol’`: The Verifier decrypts the colourings of the vertices connected by the requested edge.
14. `passCol’`: The colourings of the two vertices are different.
15. `failCol’`: The colourings of the two vertices are the same or use an unrecognised colour.

As actions marked with a ' are meant to be equivalent, functions like `pre` and relations like \sim will be the same, with instances of the agent P replaced with agent S for the simulator. The only notable change is that the states of the epistemic model w and \bar{w} are still indistinguishable for the simulator, thus $w \sim_S \bar{w}$. In this simulator, the new actions `ranEdge` and `genCol` have n and 6 many possible results, respectively, and so are assigned new propositions e'_i and d'_j . They have preconditions $\text{pre}(\text{ranEdge}_1) = e'_1 \wedge \neg(e'_2 \vee \dots \vee e'_n)$, $\text{pre}(\text{genCol}_1) = d'_1 \wedge \neg(d'_2 \vee \dots \vee d'_6)$ and so on. Their dependencies are $\text{dep}(\text{ranEdge}_i) = \top$ and $\text{dep}(\text{genCol}_j) = \bigvee_{i=1}^n \text{ranEdge}_i$.

From the addition of these propositions, we can deduce when the simulator would pass or fail in the proof system. Given a proposition representing a randomly generated edge e'_i with a valid colouring, the proof system would pass if and only if the edge requested by the Verifier is the same. That is, only states in which e'_i and e_i are true. Hence, we can modify the precondition of `passCol'` to $\text{pre}(\text{passCol}') = \bigvee_{i=1}^n (e'_i \wedge e_i)$. Similarly, $\text{pre}(\text{failCol}') = \neg \text{pre}(\text{passCol}')$.

Other than this, as `choKey'` and everything afterwards is equivalent in both protocols, we can merge these equivalent actions under their original names with some updates to dependencies. Namely, $\text{dep}(\text{choKey}) = \bigvee_{j=1}^6 \text{genCol}_j \vee \text{appDer}$. This allows a representation of the Verifier's inability to distinguish between the actions unique to the Prover and those unique to the simulator.

Naturally, we have $\text{ranEdge}_i \sim_V \text{genCol}_j \sim_V \iota \sim_c \text{genCol}_j \sim_c \text{ranEdge}_i$. If the Prover and simulator are represented separately, we can include their inability to distinguish between each other's actions, but that isn't useful for this analysis and would prevent the action merging done earlier. As such, it is ignored.

In terms of information sets, the information held by the simulator is only as much as the Verifier has. Therefore, we get

$$\begin{aligned} I_S(w) &= I_V(w) = I_V(\bar{w}) = I_S(\bar{w}) \quad \& \\ Ax_S(w) &= Ax_V(w) = Ax_V(\bar{w}) = Ax_S(\bar{w}). \end{aligned}$$

The divergence of their information begins in the new actions. We have

$$\begin{aligned} I_S(\text{ranEdge}_i) &= \{e'\} \quad \& \\ Ax_S(\text{ranEdge}_i) &= \{e' \in \text{Edge}\}. \end{aligned}$$

We then have $I_S(\text{genCol}_j) = \{g_1, g_2, \text{Der} : \text{Vert} \rightarrow \text{RGBX}\}$, where

$$\begin{aligned} Ax_S(\text{genCol}_j) &= \{g_1 \neq g_2, g_1 \in \text{RGB}, g_2 \in \text{RGB}, \\ &\quad \forall v \in \text{Vert}(\text{Der}(v) \in \text{RGB} \leftrightarrow \exists v' \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(e', v, v'))), \\ &\quad \forall v \in \text{Vert}(\text{Der}(v) \in \text{RGB} \rightarrow v = g_1 \vee v = g_2), \\ &\quad \forall v_1, v_2 \in \text{Vert}(\text{Con}(e', v_1, v_2) \rightarrow \text{Der}(v_1) \neq \text{Der}(v_2))\}. \end{aligned}$$

Probabilistically, the choices made at the start of the protocol are randomly generated and not chosen by an actual involved party. Thus, we can uniformly

assign a probability for each outcome and have that

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{L}(w)(\text{ranEdge}_i) &= \mathbb{L}(\bar{w})(\text{ranEdge}_i) = \frac{1}{n} \quad \& \\ \mathbb{L}(w)(\text{genCol}_j) &= \mathbb{L}(\bar{w})(\text{genCol}_j) = \frac{1}{6}.\end{aligned}$$

Having fully defined the simulator, our goal is now to prove that the original proof system is zero-knowledge. To do this, we need to draw a full equivalence between the two protocols while showing that the simulator finishes within polynomial time. Polynomial space is simple to show based on the number of states in the final epistemic model. That is, all possible states that fulfil $\text{dep}(\text{fail}) = \text{passCol}' \vee \text{failCol}'$. There are n choices from the e'_i propositions, 6 from the d' propositions, and n -many from the e_i propositions. Thus, there are $6n^2$ possible states in the result of the protocol for each state in the initial epistemic model. As the epistemic model has 2 states, there are $12n^2$ in total. Each state has an equal probability assigned to it and passing states maintain the original indistinguishability from the initial epistemic model.

Assuming uniform choice of the Verifier in the proof system, each passing instance has a $\frac{1}{6n}$ probability of occurring given a valid Prover. On the other hand, on reducing the states at the end of the simulator to only those which would pass the proof system, we have $6n$ -many states with equal probability. This similarly gives a uniform distribution over the states which is equivalent in both protocols from the perspective of the Verifier on the reduction of passing states only.

Furthermore, in any given state in the proof system where e_i and d_j are true, there is an equivalent state in the simulator in which e'_i , d'_j , and e_i are true, which represents an equivalent amount of information being given to the Verifier in both instances. Thus, every instance is reachable and equally probable in both protocols, making them indistinguishable for the Verifier.

The first-order information held by the Verifier in both protocols is the same, and all differences between protocols are indistinguishable. The probabilities and propositions are equivalent and there are no states in either the proof system or the passing simulator which don't have an analogue in the other. Hence, the protocols are indistinguishable, and the proof system must be zero-knowledge for the Verifier.

2 Circuit Satisfiability

Example. Circuit satisfiability is a problem involving a given circuit. This circuit is made up of inputs; AND, OR, and NOT gates; and an output. The problem is then whether there is a way to set the inputs such that the output is on. In comparison to the previous example, the method of committing to an answer is more involved, as it ensures that the gates are properly used.

The protocol for circuit satisfiability uses numbers with special properties in modulo arithmetic. Ignoring 0, a number x is a *quadratic residue* (QR) if there is a number r such that $r^2 = x \pmod n$. If no such number exists, it is called a *quadratic non-residue* (QNR). The protocol equates QNRs with 1 and QRs with 0. The commitment is then a sequence of numbers that represent an assignment of 1s and 0s to the inputs and outputs of the circuit and gates. Checks are done to ensure the gates are being used correctly and then the final output of the circuit is shown to be a QNR.

To show that a number is a QNR, the Verifier must have a base QNR y . For some QNR x' , the Prover can prove it is not a QR by giving the Verifier r such that $r^2 \times y = y'$. r^2 is a QR, and y is not, thus y' cannot be either.

We therefore require a preceding zero knowledge proof to give the Verifier a QNR. To prove to the Verifier that the number given is a QNR, the Prover must answer whether a requested number is QR or QNR, matching the result based on how the Verifier derived that number. However, if the number requested by the Verifier is maliciously generated, there is a whole in the security. To avoid this, we use the proof system the other way around, where the Verifier proves to the Prover that the request was honestly made without divulging knowledge on whether the request was a QR or not.

This example focuses on representing more complicated protocols in the framework, as such, the probabilities and proving of properties have been skipped. Similarly, as modulo arithmetic is finite in size, it can inherently be defined in first-order logic, so that has been skipped for brevity.

2.1 Quadratic Non-Residue (Request Validity)

The relationship between Prover and Verifier are flipped in this instance since it is the Verifier proving to the Prover that their request is valid before the Prover actually engages with the quadratic non-residue zero-knowledge proof. Protocol:

1. The Verifier generates a number r_0 and the set $R = \{r_1, \dots, r_{2n}\}$.
2. The Verifier generates a set S of n random elements of the form $r_i^2 \pmod N$ of elements $i = 1, \dots, n$.
3. The Verifier generates a set T of n random elements of the form $r_i^2 \times y \pmod N$ of elements $i = n + 1, \dots, 2n$.
4. The Verifier creates the union of these sets $U = S \cup T$.
5. The Verifier chooses the value x as either $r_0^2 \pmod N$ or $r_0^2 \times y \pmod N$.
6. The Verifier sends both U and x to the Prover.
7. The Prover selects n random elements from U to form Z and returns those to the Verifier.
8. The Verifier ensures that all elements of Z are in U .
9. The Verifier gets all the elements of R that formed the elements in Z and puts them in Z' .
10. However many more elements in Z' are from S than from T , the Verifier randomly selects from S and puts in dS .
11. However many more elements in Z' are from T than from S , the Verifier randomly selects from T and puts in dT .
12. The Verifier sends Z' , dS , dT to the Prover.
13. The Prover checks that all answers from these are correct and that the remaining elements of U are more than $\frac{n}{3}$.
14. The Verifier puts all remaining elements of U that have a square root in X , and the other remaining elements in Y .
15. If x has a square root modulo N :

$$X' = \{\sqrt{x \times x_i} = r_0 \times r_i \mid x_i \in X\}$$

$$Y' = \{\sqrt{x \times y_i \times y} = y \times r_0 \times r_i \mid y_i \in Y\}$$

If x does not have a square root modulo N :

$$X' = \{\sqrt{x \times x_i \times y} = y \times r_0 \times r_i \mid x_i \in X\}$$

$$Y' = \{\sqrt{x \times y_i} = r_0 \times r_i \mid y_i \in Y\}$$

16. The Verifier creates the set $U' = X' \cup Y'$ and sends it to the Prover.
17. The Prover checks all values of U' are correct:

$$\forall u \in U' (u^2 \times x \in U \vee u^2 \times x \times y \in U)$$

Simulator:

1. The Simulator generates a random x and the set $R = \{r_1, \dots, r_{2n}\}$.
2. The Simulator selects r'_1, \dots, r'_n random elements from R and forms R' .

3. For all elements $r'_i \in R'$, the Simulator randomly performs $r_i'^2$ or $r_i'^2 \times y$ and puts the result in U .
4. However many more elements in U of either operation than there are of the other, the Simulator takes the same number of elements from $R \setminus R'$ and adds them to U after performing the lesser operation.
5. For the remaining (even number of) elements of R yet to be added, half of them are added to U after the operation $r_i^2 \times x$ and the other half the operation $r_i^2 \times x \times y$.
6. The Simulator sends U to the Prover.
7. The Prover selects n -many elements of U and forms Z , sending it to the Simulator.
8. If Z contains only elements of the form r_i^2 and $r_i^2 \times y$, and all of the elements of one of those forms, we continue.
9. The Simulator responds with all of the elements of R used in U to form r_i^2 and $r_i^2 \times y$, either in Z' , dS , or dT as in the original protocol, and sends them to the Prover.
10. The Prover verifies that the elements of Z' are valid.
11. The Simulator puts the remaining elements of R in U' and sends those to the Prover.
12. The Prover verifies that the elements of U' are correct.

Action model:

```

– V: genR    choS    choT    setU    QRx    QNRx    sendCom
– P: recCom  choZ    sendZ
– V: recZ    ansZ    ansdS    ansdT    sendAns
– P: recAns  passAns  failAns  passSize  failSize
– V: setXY   setQRX'Y'  setQNRX'Y'  setU'    sendU'
– P: recU'   passEls   failEls
    
```

Simulator model:

```

– S: genR    choST    chodSdT  setU'    genx    sendCom
– P: recCom  choZ    sendZ
– S: recZ    ansZ    ansdS    ansdT    sendAns
– P: recAns  passAns  failAns  passSize  failSize
– S: setU''  sendU'
– P: recU'   passEls  failEls
    
```

Dependencies:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{dep}(\text{genR}) = \top, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{choS}) = \text{dep}(\text{choT}) = \text{dep}(\text{QRx}) = \text{dep}(\text{QNRx}) = \text{genR}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{setU}) = \text{choS} \wedge \text{choT}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{sendCom}) = \text{setU} \wedge (\text{QRx} \vee \text{QNRx}), \\
& \text{dep}(\text{recCom}) = \text{sendCom}, \qquad \text{dep}(\text{choZ}) = \text{recCom}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{sendZ}) = \text{choZ}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{recZ}) = \text{sendZ}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{ansZ}) = \text{dep}(\text{ansdS}) = \text{dep}(\text{ansdT}) = \text{recZ}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{sendAns}) = \text{ansZ} \wedge \text{ansdS} \wedge \text{ansdT}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{recAns}) = \text{sendAns}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{passAns}) = \text{dep}(\text{failAns}) = \text{dep}(\text{passSize}) = \text{dep}(\text{failSize}) = \text{recAns}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{setXY}) = \text{dep}(\text{setQRX}'Y') = \text{dep}(\text{setQNRX}'Y') = \text{recZ} \wedge \text{ansdS} \wedge \text{ansdT}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{setU}') = \text{setQRX}'Y' \vee \text{setQNRX}'Y', \quad \text{dep}(\text{sendU}') = \text{setU}', \\
& \text{dep}(\text{recU}') = \text{sendU}', \qquad \text{dep}(\text{passEls}) = \text{dep}(\text{failEls}) = \text{recU}', \\
& \text{dep}(\text{fin}) = (\text{passEls} \wedge \text{passSize} \wedge \text{passAns}) \vee (\text{failEls} \vee \text{failSize} \vee \text{failAns}).
\end{aligned}$$

Simulator dependencies:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{dep}(\text{choST}) = \text{dep}(\text{genx}) = \top, \qquad \text{dep}(\text{chodSdT}) = \text{genx}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{setU}') = \text{choST} \wedge \text{chodSdT}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{sendCom}) = \text{setU}' \vee (\text{setU} \wedge (\text{QRx} \vee \text{QNRx})), \\
& \text{dep}(\text{setU}'') = \text{recZ} \wedge \text{ansdS} \wedge \text{ansdT}, \\
& \text{dep}(\text{sendU}') = \text{setU}' \vee \text{setU}''.
\end{aligned}$$

Information sets:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_V(\bar{w}) &= \{N, n, y, \mathbb{Z}_N = \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\}\} \\
 Ax_V(\bar{w}) &= \{n = \log_2(N), \exists p, q(\text{prime}(p) \wedge \text{prime}(q) \wedge N = p \times q), y \in \mathbb{Z}_N, \\
 &\quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_N(\text{zero}(z) \leftrightarrow \neg \exists z' \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z' < z)), \\
 &\quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_N(\text{zero}(z) \leftrightarrow z = 0), \\
 &\quad \exists z_1, \dots, z_N \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z_1 \neq z_2 \wedge \dots \wedge z_{N-1} \neq z_N \wedge \\
 &\quad \quad \forall z' \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z' = z_1 \vee \dots \vee z' = z_N)), \\
 &\quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_N(QR(z) \leftrightarrow \exists z' \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z'^2 = z \wedge \neg \text{zero}(z'))), \\
 &\quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_N(QNR(z) \leftrightarrow \neg \exists z' \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z'^2 = z)), \\
 &\quad \text{(Finite) First-order rules for modulo arithmetic}\} \\
 I_P(\bar{w}) &= I_V(\bar{w}) \cup \{p, q\} \\
 Ax_P(\bar{w}) &= Ax_V(\bar{w}) \cup \{\text{prime}(p), \text{prime}(q), N = p \times q\} \\
 \\
 I_V(w) &= I_V(\bar{w}) \\
 Ax_V(w) &= Ax_V(\bar{w}) \\
 I_P(w) &= I_V(w) \cup \{p, q\} \\
 Ax_P(w) &= Ax_V(w) \cup \{\text{prime}(p), \text{prime}(q), N = p \times q, QNR(y)\} \\
 I_V(\text{genR}) &= \{R = \{r_0, \dots, r_{2n}\}\} \\
 Ax_V(\text{genR}) &= \{\forall r \in R(\exists i \in \mathbb{Z}_{2n}(\text{gen}(r, i))) \wedge \forall i \in \mathbb{Z}_{2n+1}(\exists r \in R(\text{gen}(r, i))), \\
 &\quad \forall r, r' \in R, \forall i, i' \in \mathbb{Z}_{2n+1}(\text{gen}(r, i) \wedge \text{gen}(r', i') \rightarrow (r = r' \leftrightarrow i = i')), \\
 &\quad \forall r \in R(r \in \mathbb{Z}_N)\} \\
 \\
 I_V(\text{choS}) &= \{S = \{s_1, \dots, s_n\}\} \\
 Ax_V(\text{choS}) &= \{\forall s \in S(\exists r \in R, i \in \mathbb{Z}_{2n+1}(\text{gen}(r, i) \wedge n < i \leq 2n \wedge s = r^2)), \\
 &\quad \forall s, s' \in S, \forall r, r' \in R(s = r^2 \wedge s' = r'^2 \rightarrow \\
 &\quad \quad (r = r' \leftrightarrow s = s'))\} \\
 \\
 I_V(\text{choT}) &= \{T = \{t_1, \dots, t_n\}\} \\
 Ax_V(\text{choT}) &= \{\forall t \in T(\exists r \in R, i \in \mathbb{Z}_{2n+1}(\text{gen}(r, i) \wedge n < i \leq 2n \wedge s = r^2 \times y)), \\
 &\quad \forall t, t' \in T, \forall r, r' \in R(t = r^2 \times y \wedge t' = r'^2 \times y \rightarrow \\
 &\quad \quad (r = r' \leftrightarrow t = t'))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_V(\text{QRx}) &= \{x\} \\
A_{X_V}(\text{QRx}) &= \{\exists r_0 \in \mathbb{R}(\text{gen}(r_0, 0) \wedge x = r_0^2)\} \\
\\
I_V(\text{QNRx}) &= \{x\} \\
A_{X_V}(\text{QNRx}) &= \{\exists r_0 \in \mathbb{R}(\text{gen}(r_0, 0) \wedge x = r_0^2 \times y)\} \\
\\
I_V(\text{setU}) &= \{U = \{u_1, \dots, u_{2n}\}\} \\
A_{X_V}(\text{setU}) &= \{\forall u(u \in U \leftrightarrow u \in S \vee u \in T) \wedge \neg \exists u(u \in S \wedge u \in T)\} \\
I_c(\text{sendCom}) &= \{U = \{u_1, \dots, u_{2n}\}\} \\
A_{X_c}(\text{sendCom}) &= \{\forall u \in U(u \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge u \neq 0), \\
&\quad \exists u_1, \dots, u_{2n} \in U(u_1 \neq u_2 \wedge \dots \wedge u_{2n-1} \neq u_{2n} \wedge \\
&\quad \forall u' \in U(u' = u_1 \vee \dots \vee u' = u_{2n}))\} \\
I_P(\text{recCom}) &= \{U = \{u_1, \dots, u_{2n}\}\} \\
A_{X_P}(\text{recCom}) &= \{\forall u \in U(u \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge u \neq 0), \\
&\quad \exists u_1, \dots, u_{2n} \in U(u_1 \neq u_2 \wedge \dots \wedge u_{2n-1} \neq u_{2n} \wedge \\
&\quad \forall u' \in U(u' = u_1 \vee \dots \vee u' = u_{2n}))\} \\
\\
I_P(\text{choZ}) &= \{Z = \{z_1, \dots, z_n\}\} \\
A_{X_P}(\text{choZ}) &= \{\forall z \in Z(z \in U), \\
&\quad \exists z_1, \dots, z_n \in Z(z_1 \neq z_2 \wedge \dots \wedge z_{n-1} \neq z_n \wedge \\
&\quad \forall z' \in Z(z' = z_1 \vee \dots \vee z' = z_n))\} \\
\\
I_c(\text{sendZ}) &= \{Z = \{z_1, \dots, z_n\}\} \\
A_{X_c}(\text{sendZ}) &= \{\forall z \in Z(z \in U), \\
&\quad \exists z_1, \dots, z_n \in Z(z_1 \neq z_2 \wedge \dots \wedge z_{n-1} \neq z_n \wedge \\
&\quad \forall z' \in Z(z' = z_1 \vee \dots \vee z' = z_n))\} \\
\\
I_V(\text{recZ}) &= \{Z = \{z_1, \dots, z_n\}\} \\
A_{X_V}(\text{recZ}) &= \{\forall z \in Z(z \in U), \\
&\quad \exists z_1, \dots, z_n \in Z(z_1 \neq z_2 \wedge \dots \wedge z_{n-1} \neq z_n \wedge \\
&\quad \forall z' \in Z(z' = z_1 \vee \dots \vee z' = z_n))\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_V(\text{ansZ}) &= \{\text{Ans} = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}\} \\
 \text{Ax}_V(\text{ansZ}) &= \{\forall a \in \text{Ans}(a \in \mathbb{R}), \\
 &\quad \forall a \in \text{Ans}(\exists z \in \mathbb{Z}(z = a^2 \vee z = a^2 \times y)), \\
 &\quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}(\exists a \in \text{Ans}(z = a^2 \vee z = a^2 \times y)), \\
 &\quad \text{lf}_{p_{\text{zipZ}}}(z_s, z_t)[z_s \in \mathbb{S} \wedge z_t \in \mathbb{T} \wedge z_s \in \mathbb{Z} \wedge z_t \in \mathbb{Z} \wedge \\
 &\quad (\forall z \in \mathbb{Z}(z \in \mathbb{S} \rightarrow z_s \leq z \wedge z \in \mathbb{T} \rightarrow z_t \leq z) \vee \\
 &\quad \exists z'_s \in \mathbb{S}, z'_t \in \mathbb{T}(z'_s \in \mathbb{Z} \wedge z'_t \in \mathbb{Z} \wedge z'_s < z_s \wedge z'_t < z_t \wedge \\
 &\quad \text{zipZ}(z'_s, z'_t)) \wedge \neg \exists z''_s \in \mathbb{S}(z'_s < z''_s < z_s) \wedge \\
 &\quad \neg \exists z''_t \in \mathbb{T}(z'_t < z''_t < z_t))], \\
 &\quad \forall z_s \in \mathbb{Z}(z_s \in \mathbb{S} \rightarrow \exists z_t \in \mathbb{Z}(\text{zipS}(z_s, z_t))) \vee \\
 &\quad \forall z_t \in \mathbb{Z}(z_t \in \mathbb{T} \rightarrow \exists z_s \in \mathbb{Z}(\text{zipS}(z_s, z_t)))]\} \\
 \\
 I_V(\text{ansdS}) &= \{\text{dS} = \{ds_1, \dots\}\} \\
 \text{Ax}_V(\text{ansdS}) &= \{\forall ds \in \text{dS}(ds \in \mathbb{R} \wedge ds^2 \in \mathbb{U} \wedge \neg(ds \in \mathbb{Z})), \\
 &\quad \text{lf}_{p_{\text{zipS}}}(ds, z_t)[ds \in \text{dS} \wedge z_t \in \mathbb{T} \wedge z_t \in \mathbb{Z} \wedge \\
 &\quad (\forall z'_t \in \mathbb{Z}(z'_t \in \mathbb{T} \wedge z'_t < z_t \rightarrow \exists z_s \in \mathbb{S}(\text{zipZ}(z_s, z'_t))) \wedge \\
 &\quad \forall ds' \in \text{dS}(ds \leq ds')) \vee \\
 &\quad (\exists ds' \in \text{dS}, z'_t \in \mathbb{Z}(ds' < ds \wedge z'_t < z_t \wedge \\
 &\quad \text{zipS}(ds', z'_t) \wedge \neg \exists ds'' \in \text{dS}(ds' < ds'' < ds)) \wedge \\
 &\quad \neg \exists z''_t \in \mathbb{T}(z'_t \in \mathbb{Z} \wedge dt' < dt'' < dt))], \\
 &\quad \forall ds \in \text{dS}(\exists z_t \in \mathbb{Z}(\text{zipS}(ds, z_t)))]\} \\
 \\
 I_V(\text{ansdT}) &= \{\text{dT} = \{dt_1, \dots\}\} \\
 \text{Ax}_V(\text{ansdT}) &= \{\forall dt \in \text{dT}(dt \in \mathbb{R} \wedge dt^2 \times y \in \mathbb{U} \wedge \neg(dt \in \mathbb{Z})), \\
 &\quad \text{lf}_{p_{\text{zipT}}}(z_s, dt)[z_s \in \mathbb{S} \wedge z_s \in \mathbb{Z} \wedge dt \in \text{dT} \wedge \\
 &\quad (\forall z'_s \in \mathbb{Z}(z'_s \in \mathbb{S} \wedge z'_s < z_s \rightarrow \exists z_t \in \mathbb{T}(\text{zipZ}(z'_s, z_t))) \wedge \\
 &\quad \forall dt' \in \text{dT}(dt \leq dt')) \vee \\
 &\quad (\exists dt' \in \text{dT}, z'_s \in \mathbb{Z}(dt' < dt \wedge z'_s < z_s \wedge \\
 &\quad \text{zipT}(z'_s, dt') \wedge \neg \exists dt'' \in \text{dT}(dt' < dt'' < dt) \wedge \\
 &\quad \neg \exists z''_s \in \mathbb{S}(z''_s \in \mathbb{Z} \wedge z'_s < z''_s < z_s))], \\
 &\quad \forall dt \in \text{dT}(\exists z_s \in \mathbb{Z}(\text{zipT}(z_s, dt)))]\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_c(\text{sendAns}) &= \{\text{Ans} = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}, dS = \{ds_1, \dots\}, dT = \{dt_1, \dots\}\} \\
A_{X_c}(\text{sendAns}) &= \{\forall a \in \text{Ans}, ds \in dS, dt \in dT (a \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge ds \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge dt \in \mathbb{Z}_N)\} \\
I_P(\text{recAns}) &= \{\text{Ans} = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}, dS = \{ds_1, \dots\}, dT = \{dt_1, \dots\}\} \\
A_{X_P}(\text{recAns}) &= \{\forall a \in \text{Ans}, ds \in dS, dt \in dT (a \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge ds \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge dt \in \mathbb{Z}_N)\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_P(\text{passAns}) &= \emptyset \\
A_{X_P}(\text{passAns}) &= \{\forall a \in \text{Ans} (\exists z \in Z (a^2 = z) \vee \exists z \in Z (a^2 \times y = z)), \\
&\quad \forall z \in Z (\exists a \in \text{Ans} (a^2 = z) \vee \exists a \in \text{Ans} (a^2 \times y)), \\
&\quad \forall ds \in dS (ds^2 \in U), \forall dt \in dT (dt^2 \times y \in U), \\
&\quad \text{Similar least-fixed point formulas } (ZipZ, ZipS, ZipT)\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_P(\text{failAns}) &= \emptyset \\
A_{X_P}(\text{failAns}) &= \{\exists z \in Z, ds \in dS, dt \in dT (\\
&\quad \neg(z^2 \in U \vee z^2 \times y \in U \vee \\
&\quad ds^2 \in U \vee dt^2 \times y \in U))\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_P(\text{passSize}) &= \emptyset \\
A_{X_P}(\text{passSize}) &= \{\exists u_1, \dots, u_{\frac{3n}{8}} \in U (\neg \exists z \in Z, ds \in dS, dt \in dT (\\
&\quad z^2 = u_1 \vee z^2 \times y = u_1 \vee ds^2 = u_1 \vee \\
&\quad dt^2 \times y = u_1 \vee \dots \vee dt^2 \times y = u_{\frac{3n}{8}}))\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_P(\text{failSize}) &= \emptyset \\
A_{X_P}(\text{failSize}) &= \{\neg (\exists u_1, \dots, u_{\frac{3n}{8}} \in U (\neg \exists z \in Z, ds \in dS, dt \in dT (\\
&\quad z^2 = u_1 \vee z^2 \times y = u_1 \vee ds^2 = u_1 \vee \\
&\quad dt^2 \times y = u_1 \vee \dots \vee dt^2 \times y = u_{\frac{3n}{8}})))\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_V(\text{setXY}) &= \{X = \{x_1, \dots\}, Y = \{y_1, \dots\}\} \\
 A_{X_V}(\text{setXY}) &= \{\forall x_i(x_i \in X \leftrightarrow x_i \in S \wedge \neg(x_i \in Z) \wedge \neg \exists ds \in dS(x_i = ds^2 \times y)), \\
 &\quad \forall y_i(y_i \in Y \leftrightarrow y_i \in T \wedge \neg(y_i \in Z) \wedge \neg \exists dt \in dT(y_i = dt^2))\} \\
 \\
 I_V(\text{setQRX'Y'}) &= \{X' = \{x'_1, \dots\}, Y' = \{y'_1, \dots\}\} \\
 A_{X_V}(\text{setQRX'Y'}) &= \{\forall x' \in X'(\exists x \in X, r, r_0 \in R(r^2 = x \wedge \text{gen}(r_0, 0) \wedge r \times r_0 = x')), \\
 &\quad \forall y' \in Y'(\exists y \in Y, r, r_0 \in R(r^2 \times y = y \wedge \text{gen}(r_0, 0) \wedge y \times r \times r_0 = x'))\} \\
 \\
 I_V(\text{setQNRX'Y'}) &= \{X' = \{x'_1, \dots\}, Y' = \{y'_1, \dots\}\} \\
 A_{X_V}(\text{setQNRX'Y'}) &= \{\forall x' \in X'(\exists x \in X, r, r_0 \in R(r^2 = x \wedge \text{gen}(r_0, 0) \wedge y \times r \times r_0 = x')), \\
 &\quad \forall y' \in Y'(\exists y \in Y, r, r_0 \in R(r^2 \times y = x \wedge \text{gen}(r_0, 0) \wedge r \times r_0 = x'))\} \\
 \\
 I_V(\text{setU}') &= \{U' = \{u'_1, \dots\}\} \\
 A_{X_V}(\text{setU}') &= \{\forall u' \in U'(u' \in X' \vee u' \in Y', \\
 &\quad \forall x' \in X', y' \in Y'(x' \in U' \wedge y' \in U'))\} \\
 \\
 I_c(\text{sendU}') &= \{U' = \{u'_1, \dots\}\} \\
 A_{X_c}(\text{sendU}') &= \{\forall u' \in U'(u' \in \mathbb{Z}_N)\} \\
 I_P(\text{recU}') &= \{U' = \{u'_1, \dots\}\} \\
 A_{X_P}(\text{recU}') &= \{\forall u' \in U'(u' \in \mathbb{Z}_N)\} \\
 \\
 I_P(\text{passEls}) &= \emptyset \\
 A_{X_P}(\text{passEls}) &= \{\forall u' \in U'(u'^2 \times x \in U \vee u'^2 \times x \times y \in U)\} \\
 \\
 I_P(\text{failEls}) &= \emptyset \\
 A_{X_P}(\text{failEls}) &= \{\exists u' \in U'(\neg(u'^2 \times x \in U) \wedge \neg(u'^2 \times x \times y \in U))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Simulator information set:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_S(\text{choST}) &= \{R' = \{r_1, \dots\}, ST = \{st_1, \dots\}\} \\
A_{X_S}(\text{choST}) &= \{\forall r \in R'(r \in R \wedge \neg(\text{gen}(r, 0))), \\
&\quad \forall st \in ST(\exists r \in R'(r^2 = st \vee r^2 \times y = st)), \\
&\quad \exists st_1, \dots, st_n(st_1 \neq st_2 \wedge \dots \wedge st_{n-1} \neq st_n), \\
&\quad \forall r \in R'(\exists st \in ST(r^2 = st \vee r^2 \times y = st)), \\
&\quad \text{lfp}_{\text{zipST}}(s, t)[s \in ST \wedge t \in TT \wedge \\
&\quad \quad \exists r, r' \in R'(r^2 = s \wedge r'^2 \times y = t) \wedge \\
&\quad \quad \forall st \in ST((\exists r \in R'(r^2 = st) \rightarrow s \leq st) \wedge \\
&\quad \quad \quad \exists r \in R'(r^2 \times y = st) \rightarrow t \leq st) \vee \\
&\quad \quad \exists s', t' \in ST(\exists r, r' \in R'(r^2 = s' \wedge r'^2 \times y = t') \wedge \\
&\quad \quad \quad s' \leq s \wedge t' \leq t \wedge \text{zipST}(s', t') \wedge \\
&\quad \quad \quad \forall st \in ST(\exists r \in R'(r^2 = st) \rightarrow \neg(s' \leq st \leq s) \wedge \\
&\quad \quad \quad \exists r \in R'(r^2 \times y = st) \rightarrow \neg(t' \leq st \leq t))], \\
&\quad \forall st \in ST((\exists r \in R'(r^2 = st) \rightarrow \exists t \in ST(\text{zipST}(st, t))) \wedge \\
&\quad \quad (\exists r \in R'(r^2 \times y = st) \rightarrow \exists s \in ST(\text{zipST}(s, st))))\} \\
\\
I_S(\text{genx}) &= \{x\} \\
A_{X_S}(\text{genx}) &= \{x \in \mathbb{Z}_N\} \\
\\
I_S(\text{chodSdT}) &= \{dSdT = \{d_1, \dots\}\} \\
A_{X_S}(\text{chodSdT}) &= \{\forall d \in dSdT(\exists r \in R(\neg(r \in R' \vee \text{gen}(r, 0)) \wedge \\
&\quad (r^2 \times x = d \vee r^2 \times x \times y = d))), \\
&\quad \forall r \in R(\neg(r \in R' \vee \text{gen}(r, 0)) \rightarrow \\
&\quad \quad \exists d \in dSdT(r^2 \times x = d \vee r^2 \times x \times y = d))\} \\
\\
I_S(\text{setU}') &= \{U' = \{u'_1, \dots, u'_{2n}\}\} \\
A_{X_S}(\text{setU}') &= \{\forall u \in U'(u \in ST \vee u \in dSdT), \\
&\quad \forall st \in ST, d \in dSdT(st \in U' \wedge d \in U')\}
\end{aligned}$$

2.2 Quadratic Non-Residue (Check)

Protocol:

1. The Verifier randomly generates r_0 .
2. The Verifier calculates either $x = r_0^2$ or $x = r_0^2 \times y$.
3. The Verifier sends x to the Prover.
4. The Prover tells the Verifier whether x is a quadratic residue.
5. The Verifier ensures that x is a quadratic residue if and only if it was formed by r_0^2 .

Simulator:

1. The Verifier randomly generates r_0 .
2. The Verifier calculates either $x = r_0^2$ or $x = r_0^2 \times y$.
3. The Verifier sends x to the Simulator.
4. The Simulator randomly chooses to tell the Verifier that x is or is not a quadratic residue.
5. The Verifier ensures that x is a quadratic residue if and only if $x = r_0^2$.

Action model:

- V: `genr` `QRx` `QNRx` `sendx`
- P: `recx` `checkQRx` `checkQNRx` `sendAns`
- V: `recAns` `passAns` `failAns`

Simulator model:

- V: `genr` `QRx` `QNRx` `sendx`
- S: `recx` `randQRx` `randQNRx` `sendAns`
- V: `recAns` `passAns` `failAns`

Dependencies:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{dep}(\text{genr}) &= \top, & \text{dep}(\text{QRx}) &= \text{dep}(\text{QNRx}) = \text{genr}, \\
 \text{dep}(\text{sendx}) &= \text{QRx} \vee \text{QNRx}, \\
 \\
 \text{dep}(\text{recx}) &= \text{sendx}, & \text{dep}(\text{checkQRx}) &= \text{QRx} \wedge \text{recx}, \\
 \text{dep}(\text{checkQNRx}) &= \text{QNRx} \wedge \text{recx}, & \text{dep}(\text{sendAns}) &= \text{checkQRx} \vee \text{checkQNRx}, \\
 \\
 \text{dep}(\text{recAns}) &= \text{sendAns}, & \text{dep}(\text{passAns}) &= \text{dep}(\text{failAns}) = \text{recAns}, \\
 \text{dep}(\text{fin}) &= \text{passAns} \vee \text{failAns}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Simulator dependencies:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{dep}(\text{randQRx}) &= \text{dep}(\text{randQNRx}) = \text{recx}, \\
 \text{dep}(\text{sendAns}) &= \text{checkQRx} \vee \text{checkQNRx} \vee \text{randQRx} \vee \text{randQNRx}
 \end{aligned}$$

Information Set:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_V(\bar{w}) &= \{N, n, y, \mathbb{Z}_N = \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\}\} \\
Ax_V(\bar{w}) &= \{n = \log_2(N), \exists p, q \in \mathbb{Z}_N(\text{prime}(p) \wedge \text{prime}(q) \wedge N = p \times q), y \in \mathbb{Z}_N, \\
&\quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_N(\text{zero}(z) \leftrightarrow \neg \exists z' \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z' < z)), \\
&\quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_N(\text{zero}(z) \leftrightarrow z = 0), \\
&\quad \exists z_1, \dots, z_N \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z_1 \neq z_2 \wedge \dots \wedge z_{N-1} \neq z_N \wedge \\
&\quad \quad \forall z' \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z' = z_1 \vee \dots \vee z' = z_N)), \\
&\quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_N(QR(z) \leftrightarrow \exists z' \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z'^2 = z \wedge \neg \text{zero}(z'))), \\
&\quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_N(QNR(z) \leftrightarrow \neg \exists z' \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z'^2 = z)), \\
&\quad \text{(Finite) First-order rules for modulo arithmetic}\} \\
I_P(\bar{w}) &= I_V(\bar{w}) \cup \{p, q\} \\
Ax_P(\bar{w}) &= Ax_V(\bar{w}) \cup \{\text{prime}(p), \text{prime}(q), N = p \times q\} \\
\\
I_V(w) &= I_V(\bar{w}) \\
Ax_V(w) &= Ax_V(\bar{w}) \\
I_P(w) &= I_V(w) \cup \{p, q\} \\
Ax_P(w) &= Ax_V(w) \cup \{\text{prime}(p), \text{prime}(q), N = p \times q, QNR(y)\} \\
\\
I_V(\text{genr}) &= \{r_0\} \\
Ax_V(\text{genr}) &= \{r_0 \in \mathbb{Z}_N\} \\
\\
I_V(QRx) &= \{x\} \\
Ax_V(QRx) &= \{x = r_0^2\} \\
\\
I_V(QNRx) &= \{x\} \\
Ax_V(QNRx) &= \{x = r_0^2 \times y\} \\
\\
I_c(\text{sendx}) &= \{x\} \\
Ax_c(\text{sendx}) &= \{x \in \mathbb{Z}_N\} \\
I_P(\text{recx}) &= \{x\} \\
Ax_P(\text{recx}) &= \{x \in \mathbb{Z}_N\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_P(\text{checkQRx}) &= \{r\} \\
Ax_P(\text{checkQRx}) &= \{r^2 = x\} \\
\\
I_P(\text{checkQNRx}) &= \{r\} \\
Ax_P(\text{checkQNRx}) &= \{r^2 \times y = x\} \\
\\
I_c(\text{sendAns}) &= \{a\} \\
Ax_c(\text{sendAns}) &= \{QR(a)\} \\
I_V(\text{recAns}) &= \{a\} \\
Ax_V(\text{recAns}) &= \{QNR(a)\} \\
\\
I_V(\text{passAns}) &= \emptyset \\
Ax_V(\text{passAns}) &= \{QR(a) \wedge QR(x) \vee QNR(a) \wedge QNR(x)\} \\
\\
I_V(\text{failAns}) &= \emptyset \\
Ax_V(\text{failAns}) &= \{QR(a) \wedge QNR(x) \vee QNR(a) \wedge QR(x)\}
\end{aligned}$$

Simulator information set:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_S(\text{randQRx}) &= \{a\} \\
Ax_S(\text{randQRx}) &= \{QR(a)\} \\
\\
I_S(\text{randQNRx}) &= \{a\} \\
Ax_S(\text{randQNRx}) &= \{QNR(a)\}
\end{aligned}$$

2.3 Boolean Circuit (Loop)

Protocol:

1. The Prover generates a truth table for each input box, gate, and output box (Of which there is one) in the circuit.
2. A gate's output is joined to its input, but the order between possible inputs is shuffled. (An OR gate with 000-011-101-111 could also be 101-111-000-011).
3. All values of 1s and 0s respectively are replaced with unique quadratic non-residues (QNR) (Using y) and quadratic residues (QR) modulo N .
4. This is sent to the Verifier.
5. Choosing a random truth table, the Verifier either requests to see it in full (Open), or for the valid cell (Point).
6. For an Open request, the Prover sends the Verifier the answers to show which numbers are QR (0) and which are QNR (1).
7. The Verifier checks that the resulting truth table is valid.
8. For a View request, the Prover tells the Verifier which of the cells within the truth table are valid.
9. Repeat.

Simulator:

1. The Simulator picks a gate at random.
2. The Simulator randomly assigns this gate either a valid truth table or makes them all quadratic non-residue (1).
3. Verifier chooses a gate and requests to have it Open or Point to the valid cell.
4. If this is the gate chosen by the Simulator with a valid truth table, an Open request is fulfilled.
5. If this is the gate chosen by the Simulator full of 1s, a Point request is fulfilled and the Simulator responds with a random cell.
6. Repeat.

Action model:

- P: genTTs randTTs sendCom
- V: recCom choTT_i choView choPoint sendCho
- P: recCho viewTT cellTT sendAns
- V: recAns passView failView passCell

Simulator model:

- S: choTT'_i QNRTT truTT sendCom
- V: recCom choTT_i choView choPoint sendCho
- S: recCho viewTT cellTT sendAns
- V: recAns passView failView passCell

Dependencies:

$$\text{dep}(\text{genTTs}) = \top, \quad \text{dep}(\text{sendCom}) = \text{genTTs},$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dep}(\text{recCom}) &= \text{sendCom}, \\ \text{dep}(\text{choTT}_i) &= \text{dep}(\text{choView}) = \text{dep}(\text{choPoint}) = \text{recCom}, \\ \text{dep}(\text{sendCho}) &= (\bigvee_{i=1}^n \text{choTT}_i) \wedge (\text{choView} \vee \text{choPoint}), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dep}(\text{recCho}) &= \text{sendCho}, & \text{dep}(\text{viewTT}) &= \text{dep}(\text{cellTT}) = \text{recCho}, \\ \text{dep}(\text{sendAns}) &= \text{viewTT} \vee \text{cellTT}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dep}(\text{recAns}) &= \text{sendAns}, \\ \text{dep}(\text{passView}) &= \text{dep}(\text{failView}) = \text{dep}(\text{passCell}) = \text{recAns}, \\ \text{dep}(\text{fin}) &= \text{passView} \vee \text{failView} \vee \text{passCell}. \end{aligned}$$

Simulator dependencies:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dep}(\text{choTT}'_i) &= \top, & \text{dep}(\text{QNRTT}) &= \text{dep}(\text{truTT}) = \bigvee_{i=1}^n \text{choTT}_i, \\ \text{dep}(\text{sendCom}) &= \text{QNRTT} \vee \text{truTT} \end{aligned}$$

Information Set:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_V(\bar{w}) &= \{N, n, y, \mathbb{Z}_N = \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\}, G = \{g_1, \dots\}, \\
&\quad \text{In} = \{i_1, \dots\}, \text{Out} = \{o\}, W = \{w_1, \dots\}\} \\
Ax_V(\bar{w}) &= \{n = \log_2(N), \exists p, q \in \mathbb{Z}_N(\text{prime}(p) \wedge \text{prime}(q) \wedge N = p \times q), \\
&\quad y \in \mathbb{Z}_N, \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_N(\text{zero}(z) \leftrightarrow \neg \exists z' \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z' < z)), \\
&\quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_N(\text{zero}(z) \leftrightarrow z = 0), \\
&\quad \exists z_1, \dots, z_N \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z_1 \neq z_2 \wedge \dots \wedge z_{N-1} \neq z_N \wedge \\
&\quad \quad \forall z' \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z' = z_1 \vee \dots \vee z' = z_N)), \\
&\quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_N(QR(z) \leftrightarrow \exists z' \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z'^2 = z \wedge \neg \text{zero}(z'))), \\
&\quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_N(QNR(z) \leftrightarrow \neg \exists z' \in \mathbb{Z}_N(z'^2 = z)), \\
&\quad \text{(Finite) First-order rules for modulo arithmetic}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\forall g \in G((\text{and}(g) \vee \text{or}(g) \vee \text{not}(g)) \wedge \\
&\quad \neg((\text{and}(g) \wedge (\text{or}(g) \vee \text{not}(g)) \vee \text{or}(g) \wedge \text{not}(g))))), \\
&\forall g \in G(\text{and}(g) \rightarrow ((\text{in}A(g) \wedge \text{in}B(g)) \leftrightarrow \text{out}(g))), \\
&\forall g \in G(\text{or}(g) \rightarrow ((\text{in}A(g) \vee \text{in}B(g)) \leftrightarrow \text{out}(g))), \\
&\forall g \in G(\text{not}(g) \rightarrow (\text{in}A(g) \leftrightarrow \neg \text{out}(g)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\exists i(i \in \text{In}) \\
&\exists o(o \in \text{Out})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\forall w \in W(\exists i, o((i \in \text{In} \vee i \in G) \wedge (o \in G \vee o \in \text{Out})) \wedge \\
&\quad (\text{wire}A(w, i, o) \vee \text{wire}B(w, i, o))), \\
&\forall w \in W(\exists i, o(\text{wire}A(w, i, o)) \rightarrow \neg \exists i, o(\text{wire}B(w, i, o))) \\
&\forall i, o(((i \in \text{In} \vee i \in G) \wedge (o \in G \vee o \in \text{Out})) \rightarrow \\
&\quad (\text{wire}A(i, o) \leftrightarrow \exists w \in W(\text{wire}A(w, i, o))), \\
&\forall i, g(((i \in \text{In} \vee i \in G) \wedge g \in G) \rightarrow \\
&\quad (\text{wire}B(i, g) \leftrightarrow \exists w \in W(\text{wire}B(w, i, g))), \\
&\forall i, o(\text{wire}A(i, o) \rightarrow (\text{out}(i) \leftrightarrow \text{in}A(o))), \\
&\forall i, g(\text{wire}B(i, g) \rightarrow (\text{out}(i) \leftrightarrow \text{in}B(g))), \\
&\forall o \in \text{Out}(\exists i(\text{wire}A(i, o)))\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_P(\bar{w}) &= I_V(\bar{w}) \cup \{p, q\} \\
Ax_P(\bar{w}) &= Ax_V(\bar{w}) \cup \{N = p \times q\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_V(w) &= I_V(\bar{w}) \\
Ax_V(w) &= Ax_V(\bar{w})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_P(w) &= I_V(w) \cup \{p, q, \varphi = \{z_1, \dots\}\} \\
 Ax_P(w) &= Ax_V(w) \cup \{N = p \times q, \\
 &\quad \forall z \in \varphi (comA(z) \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge comB(z) \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge comOut(z) \in \mathbb{Z}_N), \\
 &\quad \forall z \in \varphi (\exists g (ans(g, z) \wedge \\
 &\quad \quad (g \in G \wedge not(g) \wedge \neg zero(comA(z)) \wedge \neg zero(comOut(z)) \wedge \\
 &\quad \quad \quad zero(comB(z))) \vee \\
 &\quad \quad (g \in G \wedge (and(g) \vee or(g)) \wedge \neg zero(comA(z)) \wedge \neg zero(comOut(z)) \wedge \\
 &\quad \quad \quad \neg zero(comB(z))) \\
 &\quad \quad (g \in In \wedge zero(comA(z)) \wedge zero(comB(z)) \wedge \neg zero(comOut(z))) \vee \\
 &\quad \quad (g \in Out \wedge QNR(comA(z)) \wedge zero(comB(z)) \wedge zero(comOut(z))))), \\
 &\quad \forall g \in G (\exists z \in \varphi (ans(g, z))) \wedge \forall i \in In (\exists z \in \varphi (ans(i, z))) \wedge \\
 &\quad \quad \forall o \in Out (\exists z \in \varphi (ans(o, z))), \\
 &\quad \forall z, z' \in \varphi, \forall g, g' (ans(g, z) \wedge ans(g', z') \rightarrow (g = g' \leftrightarrow z = z')), \\
 &\quad \forall z \in \varphi, \forall g (ans(g, z) \rightarrow ((QNR(comA(z)) \leftrightarrow inA(g)) \wedge \\
 &\quad \quad (QNR(comB(z)) \leftrightarrow inB(z)) \wedge (QNR(comOut(z)) \leftrightarrow out(g))))\} \\
 \\
 I_P(\text{genTTs}) &= \{\text{TT} = \{T_1, \dots\}\} \\
 Ax_P(\text{genTTs}) &= \{\forall T \in \text{TT} (c_1(T) \neq c_2(T) \wedge c_1(T) \neq c_3(T) \wedge c_1(T) \neq c_4(T) \wedge \\
 &\quad c_2(T) \neq c_3(T) \wedge c_2(T) \neq c_4(T) \wedge c_3(T) \neq c_4(T)) \\
 &\quad \forall T \in \text{TT}, \forall c ((c = c_1(T) \vee c = c_2(T) \vee c = c_3(T) \vee c = c_4(T)) \rightarrow \\
 &\quad \quad (comA(c) \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge comB(c) \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge comOut(c) \in \mathbb{Z}_N)), \\
 &\quad \forall T \in \text{TT} (\exists g (table(g, T) \wedge (g \in G \vee g \in In \vee g \in Out))), \\
 &\quad \forall g \in G (\exists T \in \text{TT} (table(g, T))) \wedge \forall i \in In (\exists T \in \text{TT} (table(i, T))) \wedge \\
 &\quad \quad \forall o \in Out (\exists T \in \text{TT} (table(o, T))), \\
 &\quad \forall T, T' \in \text{TT}, \forall g, g' (table(g, T) \wedge table(g', T') \rightarrow (g = g' \leftrightarrow T = T')), \\
 &\quad \forall T \in \text{TT}, \forall g \in G (table(g, T) \rightarrow (and(T) \leftrightarrow and(g)) \wedge \\
 &\quad \quad (or(T) \leftrightarrow or(g)) \wedge (not(T) \leftrightarrow not(g))), \\
 &\quad \forall T \in \text{TT}, \forall g (table(g, T) \rightarrow ((g \in In \leftrightarrow in(T)) \wedge (g \in Out \leftrightarrow out(T))))\},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall T \in \mathbf{TT}, \forall c((c = c_1(T) \vee c = c_2(T) \vee c = c_3(T) \vee c = c_4(T)) \rightarrow \\
& \quad ((\text{and}(T) \rightarrow ((QNR(\text{com}A(c)) \wedge QNR(\text{com}B(c))) \leftrightarrow \\
& \quad \quad QNR(\text{com}Out(c)))) \wedge \\
& \quad (\text{or}(T) \rightarrow ((QNR(\text{com}A(c)) \vee QNR(\text{com}B(c))) \leftrightarrow \\
& \quad \quad QNR(\text{com}Out(c)))) \wedge \\
& \quad (\text{not}(T) \rightarrow ((QNR(\text{com}A(c)) \leftrightarrow \neg QNR(\text{com}Out(c))) \wedge \\
& \quad \quad \text{zero}(\text{com}B(c)))) \wedge \\
& \quad (\text{in}(T) \rightarrow (\text{zero}(\text{com}A(c)) \wedge \text{zero}(\text{com}B(c)) \wedge \neg \text{zero}(\text{com}Out(c)))) \wedge \\
& \quad (\text{out}(T) \rightarrow (\neg \text{zero}(\text{com}A(c)) \wedge \text{zero}(\text{com}B(c)) \wedge \text{zero}(\text{com}Out(c))))), \\
& \forall T \in \mathbf{TT}, \exists c, c', c'', c''' (\\
& \quad (c = c_1(T) \vee c' = c_1(T) \vee c'' = c_1(T) \vee c''' = c_1(T)) \wedge \\
& \quad (c = c_2(T) \vee c' = c_2(T) \vee c'' = c_2(T) \vee c''' = c_2(T)) \wedge \\
& \quad (c = c_3(T) \vee c' = c_3(T) \vee c'' = c_3(T) \vee c''' = c_3(T)) \wedge \\
& \quad (c = c_4(T) \vee c' = c_4(T) \vee c'' = c_4(T) \vee c''' = c_4(T)) \wedge \\
& \quad (QNR(\text{com}A(c)) \wedge QNR(\text{com}A(c')) \wedge QR(\text{com}A(c'')) \wedge \\
& \quad \quad QR(\text{com}A(c''')) \vee \\
& \quad (\text{zero}(\text{com}A(c)) \wedge \text{zero}(\text{com}A(c')) \wedge \text{zero}(\text{com}A(c'')) \wedge \text{zero}(\text{com}A(c''')))) \\
& \quad (QNR(\text{com}B(c)) \wedge QR(\text{com}B(c')) \wedge QNR(\text{com}B(c'')) \wedge \\
& \quad \quad QR(\text{com}B(c''')) \vee \\
& \quad (\text{zero}(\text{com}B(c)) \wedge \text{zero}(\text{com}B(c')) \wedge \text{zero}(\text{com}B(c'')) \wedge \text{zero}(\text{com}B(c''')))), \\
& \forall g \in \mathbf{G}, \forall z \in \varphi, \forall T \in \mathbf{TT}(\text{table}(g, T) \wedge \text{ans}(g, z) \rightarrow \\
& \quad \exists c((c = c_1(T) \vee c = c_2(T) \vee c = c_3(T) \vee c = c_4(T)) \wedge \\
& \quad \quad (QNR(\text{com}A(z)) \wedge QNR(\text{com}A(c)) \vee \\
& \quad \quad \quad QR(\text{com}A(z)) \wedge QR(\text{com}A(c))) \wedge \\
& \quad \quad (QNR(\text{com}B(z)) \wedge QNR(\text{com}B(c)) \vee \\
& \quad \quad \quad QR(\text{com}B(z)) \wedge QR(\text{com}B(c))) \wedge \\
& \quad \quad (QNR(\text{com}Out(z)) \wedge QNR(\text{com}Out(c)) \vee \\
& \quad \quad \quad QR(\text{com}Out(z)) \wedge QR(\text{com}Out(c)))))) \}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_c(\text{sendCom}) &= \{\text{TT} = \{T_1, \dots\}\} \\
 Ax_c(\text{sendCom}) &= \{\forall T \in \text{TT}(\exists g \in G(\text{table}(g, T)) \vee \exists i \in \text{In}(\text{table}(i, T)) \vee \\
 &\quad \exists o \in \text{Out}(\text{table}(o, T))), \\
 &\quad \forall g \in G, i \in \text{In}, o \in \text{Out}(\exists T \in \text{TT}(\text{table}(g, T) \vee \\
 &\quad \text{table}(i, T) \vee \text{table}(o, T))), \\
 &\quad \forall T \in \text{TT}(\text{comA}(c_1(T)) \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge \dots \wedge \\
 &\quad \text{comOut}(c_4(T)) \in \mathbb{Z}_N)\} \\
 I_V(\text{recCom}) &= \{\text{TT} = \{T_1, \dots\}\} \\
 Ax_V(\text{recCom}) &= \{\forall T \in \text{TT}(\exists g \in G(\text{table}(g, T)) \vee \exists i \in \text{In}(\text{table}(i, T)) \vee \\
 &\quad \exists o \in \text{Out}(\text{table}(o, T))), \\
 &\quad \forall g \in G, i \in \text{In}, o \in \text{Out}(\exists T \in \text{TT}(\text{table}(g, T) \vee \\
 &\quad \text{table}(i, T) \vee \text{table}(o, T))), \\
 &\quad \forall T \in \text{TT}(\text{comA}(c_1(T)) \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge \dots \wedge \\
 &\quad \text{comOut}(c_4(T)) \in \mathbb{Z}_N)\} \\
 \\
 I_V(\text{choTT}_i) &= \{\text{ansTT}\} \\
 Ax_V(\text{choTT}_i) &= \{\exists T \in \text{TT}(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT}) = T)\} \\
 \\
 I_V(\text{choView}) &= \emptyset \\
 Ax_V(\text{choView}) &= \{\text{view}(\text{ansTT}) \wedge \neg \text{point}(\text{ansTT})\} \\
 \\
 I_V(\text{choPoint}) &= \emptyset \\
 Ax_V(\text{choPoint}) &= \{\text{point}(\text{ansTT}) \wedge \neg \text{view}(\text{ansTT})\} \\
 \\
 I_c(\text{sendCho}) &= \{\text{ansTT}\} \\
 Ax_c(\text{sendCho}) &= \{\exists T \in \text{TT}(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT}) = T), \\
 &\quad \text{view}(\text{ansTT}) \vee \text{point}(\text{ansTT})\} \\
 I_P(\text{recCho}) &= \{\text{ansTT}\} \\
 Ax_P(\text{recCho}) &= \{\exists T \in \text{TT}(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT}) = T), \\
 &\quad \text{view}(\text{ansTT}) \vee \text{point}(\text{ansTT})\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_P(\text{viewTT}) &= \{\text{resp}\} \\
A_{X_P}(\text{viewTT}) &= \{ \text{view}(\text{ansTT}), \\
&\quad QR(\text{comA}(c_1(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT}))) \rightarrow \\
&\quad \quad \text{comA}(c_1(\text{resp}))^2 = \text{comA}(c_1(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT}))), \\
&\quad QNR(\text{comA}(c_1(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT}))) \rightarrow \\
&\quad \quad \text{comA}(c_1(\text{resp}))^2 \times y = \text{comA}(c_1(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT}))), \\
&\quad \dots \\
&\quad QNR(\text{comOut}(c_4(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT}))) \rightarrow \\
&\quad \quad \text{comOut}(c_4(\text{resp}))^2 \times y = \text{comOut}(c_4(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT}))) \} \\
\\
I_P(\text{cellTT}) &= \{\text{resp}\} \\
A_{X_P}(\text{cellTT}) &= \{ \text{point}(\text{ansTT}), \\
&\quad \text{resp} = c_1(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT})) \vee \text{resp} = c_2(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT})) \vee \\
&\quad \quad \text{resp} = c_3(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT})) \vee \text{resp} = c_4(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT})) \} \\
\\
I_c(\text{sendAns}) &= \{\text{resp}\} \\
A_{X_c}(\text{sendAns}) &= \emptyset \\
I_V(\text{recAns}) &= \{\text{resp}\} \\
A_{X_V}(\text{recAns}) &= \emptyset \\
I_V(\text{passView}) &= \emptyset \\
A_{X_V}(\text{passView}) &= \{ \text{view}(\text{ansTT}), \\
&\quad \forall c((c = c_1(\text{resp}) \vee c = c_2(\text{resp}) \vee c = c_3(\text{resp}) \vee \\
&\quad \quad c = c_4(\text{resp})) \rightarrow \exists c'((c' = c_1(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT})) \vee \\
&\quad \quad c' = c_2(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT})) \vee c' = c_3(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT})) \vee \\
&\quad \quad c' = c_4(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT}))) \wedge \\
&\quad \quad (\text{comA}(c)^2 = \text{comA}(c') \vee \text{comA}(c)^2 \times y = \text{comA}(c')) \wedge \\
&\quad \quad (\text{comB}(c)^2 = \text{comB}(c') \vee \text{comB}(c)^2 \times y = \text{comB}(c')) \wedge \\
&\quad \quad (\text{comOut}(c)^2 = \text{comOut}(c') \vee \\
&\quad \quad \quad \text{comOut}(c)^2 \times y = \text{comOut}(c')) \} \\
\\
I_V(\text{failView}) &= \emptyset \\
A_{X_V}(\text{failView}) &= \{\text{Negation of a formula in passView}\} \\
\\
I_V(\text{passCell}) &= \emptyset \\
A_{X_V}(\text{passCell}) &= \{ \text{point}(\text{ansTT}), \\
&\quad \text{resp} = c_1(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT})) \vee \text{resp} = c_2(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT})) \vee \\
&\quad \quad \text{resp} = c_3(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT})) \vee \text{resp} = c_4(\text{ans}(\text{ansTT})) \}
\end{aligned}$$

Simulator information set:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_V(\text{choTT}_i) &= \{\text{choTT}\} \\
 A_{X_V}(\text{choTT}_i) &= \{\exists g \in G(\text{cho}(\text{choTT}) = g) \vee \exists i \in \text{In}(\text{cho}(\text{choTT}) = g) \vee \\
 &\quad \exists o \in \text{Out}(\text{cho}(\text{choTT}) = o)\} \\
 \\
 I_V(\text{QNR TT}) &= \{TT = \{TT_1, \dots\}\} \\
 A_{X_V}(\text{QNR TT}) &= \{\exists T \in \text{TT}(\text{table}(\text{cho}(\text{choTT}, T)) \wedge \text{QNR}(\text{comA}(c_1(T))) \wedge \\
 &\quad \dots \wedge \text{QNR}(\text{comOut}(c_4(T))))), \\
 &\quad \forall T \in \text{TT}(\exists g \in G(\text{table}(g, T)) \vee \exists i \in \text{In}(\text{table}(i, T)) \vee \\
 &\quad \exists o \in \text{Out}(\text{table}(o, T))), \\
 &\quad \forall g \in G, i \in \text{In}, o \in \text{Out}(\exists T \in \text{TT}(\text{table}(g, T) \vee \\
 &\quad \text{table}(i, T) \vee \text{table}(o, T))), \\
 &\quad \forall T \in \text{TT}(\text{comA}(c_1(T)) \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge \dots \wedge \\
 &\quad \text{comOut}(c_4(T)) \in \mathbb{Z}_N)\} \\
 \\
 I_V(\text{truTT}) &= \{TT = \{TT_1, \dots\}\} \\
 A_{X_V}(\text{truTT}) &= \{\exists T \in \text{TT}(\text{table}(\text{cho}(\text{choTT}, T)) \wedge \\
 &\quad \text{and}(T) \rightarrow (\text{QNR}(\text{comA}(c_1(T))) \wedge \\
 &\quad \text{QNR}(\text{comA}(c_1(T))) \leftrightarrow \text{QNR}(\text{comOut}(c_1(T))))), \\
 &\quad \dots \\
 &\quad \exists T \in \text{TT}(\text{table}(\text{cho}(\text{choTT}, T)) \wedge \\
 &\quad \text{out}(T) \rightarrow (\text{QNR}(\text{comOut}(c_4(T))))), \\
 &\quad \forall T \in \text{TT}(\exists g \in G(\text{table}(g, T)) \vee \exists i \in \text{In}(\text{table}(i, T)) \vee \\
 &\quad \exists o \in \text{Out}(\text{table}(o, T))), \\
 &\quad \forall g \in G, i \in \text{In}, o \in \text{Out}(\exists T \in \text{TT}(\text{table}(g, T) \vee \\
 &\quad \text{table}(i, T) \vee \text{table}(o, T))), \\
 &\quad \forall T \in \text{TT}(\text{comA}(c_1(T)) \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge \dots \wedge \\
 &\quad \text{comOut}(c_4(T)) \in \mathbb{Z}_N)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

2.4 Boolean Circuit (Check)

Protocol:

1. The Prover calculates the square roots of the products of every output with its connected input (The output of every input box or gate is connected to the input of another gate or the output box).
2. The Prover sends all of these to the Verifier.
3. The Prover sends the Verifier r such that $r^2 \times y \pmod N$ is the value in the output box.
4. The Verifier checks that the product of each end of a connection is a QR.
5. The Verifier checks that the output box is a QNR.

Simulator:

1. All pointed cells are made from QNRs, thus the output and input connection between gates are both QNRs and their product is a QR.
2. The Simulator generates these answers and sends them to the Verifier.
3. The Simulator sends the square root of the output box's value.
4. The Verifier checks these products and that the output box is a QNR.

Action model:

- P: genProdAns genOutAns sendCom
- V: recCom passProdAns failProdAns passOut failOut

Simulator model:

- S: genProdAns genOutAns sendCom
- V: recCom passProdAns failProdAns passOut failOut

Dependencies:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dep}(\text{genProdAns}) &= \text{dep}(\text{genOutAns}) = \top, \\ \text{dep}(\text{sendCom}) &= \text{genProdAns} \wedge \text{genOutAns}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dep}(\text{recCom}) &= \text{sendCom}, \\ \text{dep}(\text{passProdAns}) &= \text{dep}(\text{failProdAns}) = \text{dep}(\text{passOut}) = \text{dep}(\text{failOut}) = \text{recCom}. \end{aligned}$$

Simulator dependencies: Not applicable.

Information Set:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_V(\bar{w}) &= \{N, n, y, \mathbb{Z}_N = \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\}, G = \{g_1, \dots\}, \\
&\quad \text{In} = \{i_1, \dots\}, \text{Out} = \{o\}, \\
&\quad W = \{w_1, \dots\}, \text{AnsTT} = \{a_1, \dots\}\} \\
Ax_V(\bar{w}) &= \{\text{As the previous protocol}, \\
&\quad \forall a \in \text{AnsTT}(\text{com}A(a) \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge \text{com}B(a) \in \mathbb{Z}_N \wedge \\
&\quad \text{com}Out(a) \in \mathbb{Z}_N), \\
&\quad \forall a \in \text{AnsTT}(\exists g \in G(\text{cell}(g, a)) \vee \\
&\quad \exists i \in \text{In}(\text{cell}(i, a)) \vee \exists o \in \text{Out}(\text{cell}(o, a))), \\
&\quad \forall g \in G, i \in \text{In}, o \in \text{Out}(\exists a \in \text{AnsTT}(\text{cell}(a, g) \vee \\
&\quad \text{cell}(a, i) \vee \text{cell}(a, o)))\} \\
I_P(\bar{w}) &= \text{Not applicable} \\
Ax_P(\bar{w}) &= \text{Not applicable} \\
\\
I_V(w) &= I_V(\bar{w}) \\
Ax_V(w) &= Ax_V(\bar{w}) \\
I_P(w) &= I_V(w) \cup \{p, q, \varphi, \text{Ans}\} \\
Ax_P(w) &= Ax_V(w) \cup \{\text{As the previous protocol}, \\
&\quad \forall a \in \text{AnsTT}(\exists z \in \varphi((\text{com}A(a) = \text{com}A(z)^2 \vee \\
&\quad \text{com}A(a) = \text{com}A(z)^2 \times y) \wedge \\
&\quad (\text{com}B(a) = \text{com}B(z)^2 \vee \text{com}B(a) = \text{com}B(z)^2 \times y) \wedge \\
&\quad (\text{com}Out(a) = \text{com}Out(z)^2 \vee \\
&\quad \text{com}Out(a) = \text{com}Out(z)^2 \times y)) \leftrightarrow \\
&\quad \text{link}(a, z))(\text{Shorthand}), \\
&\quad \forall a \in \text{AnsTT}(\exists z \in \varphi(\text{link}(a, z))), \\
&\quad \forall z \in \varphi(\exists a \in \text{AnsTT}(\text{link}(a, z)))\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_P(\text{genProdAns}) &= \{\text{AnsW} = \{aw_1, \dots\}\} \\
A_{X_P}(\text{genProdAns}) &= \{\forall aw \in \text{AnsW}(\exists a, b((\\
&\quad \text{wireA}(a, b) \wedge aw^2 = \text{comOut}(a) \times \text{comA}(b)) \vee \\
&\quad (\text{wireB}(a, b) \wedge aw^2 = \text{comOut}(a) \times \text{comB}(b))))\} \\
\\
I_P(\text{genOutAns}) &= \{\text{ow}\} \\
A_{X_P}(\text{genOutAns}) &= \{\exists a \in \text{AnsTT}, o \in \text{Out}(\text{cell}(a, o) \wedge \text{comA}(o) = \text{ow}^2 \times y)\} \\
\\
I_c(\text{sendCom}) &= \{\text{AnsW} = \{aw_1, \dots\}, \text{ow}\} \\
A_{X_c}(\text{sendCom}) &= \emptyset \\
I_V(\text{recCom}) &= \{\text{AnsW} = \{aw_1, \dots\}, \text{ow}\} \\
A_{X_V}(\text{recCom}) &= \emptyset \\
\\
I_V(\text{passProdAns}) &= \emptyset \\
A_{X_V}(\text{passProdAns}) &= \{\forall aw \in \text{AnsW}(\exists a, b((\\
&\quad \text{wireA}(a, b) \wedge aw^2 = \text{comOut}(a) \times \text{comA}(b)) \vee \\
&\quad (\text{wireB}(a, b) \wedge aw^2 = \text{comOut}(a) \times \text{comB}(b))))\} \\
\\
I_V(\text{failProdAns}) &= \emptyset \\
A_{X_V}(\text{failProdAns}) &= \{\text{Negation of passProdAns}\} \\
\\
I_V(\text{passOut}) &= \emptyset \\
A_{X_V}(\text{passOut}) &= \{\exists a \in \text{AnsTT}, o \in \text{Out}(\text{cell}(a, o) \wedge \text{comA}(o) = \text{ow}^2 \times y)\} \\
\\
I_V(\text{failOut}) &= \emptyset \\
A_{X_V}(\text{failOut}) &= \{\text{Negation of passOut}\}
\end{aligned}$$

Simulator information set: Not applicable.